

DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION OF A SMART CARD FRAUD DETECTION SYSTEM USING ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORK

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Abstract: *A smart card is a plastic document with a security band and chip issued by a banking or financial entity, which is used to make purchases of product or services. Smart card is fundamental part of the economic and commercial growth of emerging and developed countries since for examples, these cards allow the transfer of money online, which contributes in an accelerated way to the expansion of electronic commerce [7]. However, as it is a very beneficial and simple payment method, it gives fraudsters ease to create fraud and money theft methods [8].*

The design of a fraud detector in smart card is a tough challenge since genuine and fraudulent behaviours are very variant and fraudsters continuously innovate their methods to avoid existing prevention measures. Data mining and machine learning techniques employ efficient probabilistic models such as: generalized regression models, artificial neural networks, decision tree, and Bayesian networks to determine and predict fraud [10]. These techniques use an autonomous learning system for the recognition of patterns and trends based on historical facts, the data of transactions made by customers are used to determine the patterns. These patterns allow to quickly identifying circumstances beyond the daily behaviour of a client that may be indications of fraud [10].

The dataset was gotten from kaggle.com and it contains transactions made by credit cards in September 2023 by European cardholders, it represents transactions that occurred in two days, where we have 492 out of 284, 807 transactions 73, notice the strong unbalancing between fraud and legal trades, typical of this kind of big business. The database contains numerical variables which have been hidden using PCA (Principal Component Analysis) transformation. These 28 features named V1, V2... V28 contain confidential data of the users and are non-reversible, thus protecting the original characteristics of the data. There are two special features that have not been transformed using PCA, these are Time and Amount. There is also an important variable called Class, which is a fundamental value in the database

Results showed that the best architecture has 25 neurons in the hidden layer, because the

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mean accuracy remains at 95.4%, which is the highest value in testing phase. This research also shows that a simple neural network is not even capable of correctly classifying the small set of selected data, so it serves as a starting point to look for a more complex architecture.

INTRODUCTION

Currently, fraud is the number one enemy in the business world. It affects industries and organizations and accounts for the big money invested in fraud prediction researching [1]. The constant growth of this problem has strongly promoted the development of new technologies to counterfeit fraudsters. The last advances in smart card fraud detection include top technology themes such as Artificial Neural Network (ANN), Deep Learning and Intelligent Agents [2] [3] [4]. In particular the implementation of agents has become important since it produces effective, quick acting monitoring of smart card fraud transactions, reducing the risk of fraud or other financial traps that could signify losses. A quick response is essential because fraudsters are constantly creating new elaborated treachery mechanisms. Most common fraud type that occurs in credit industry occurs when fraudster uses a legitimate card to undertake illegitimate transactions. The cardholder is not aware of the fact that their card is being used without their permission. The fraudster takes advantage of cardholder's ignorance by undertaking as much transactions as possible before the cardholder realizes and reports the fraud to their bank [7].

According to Laleh et al. (2009) credit

transaction fraud can be committed either offline or online [6]. Offline fraud occurs when a fraudster steals the physical card and uses it at the actual stores [6]. Although offline fraud is still popular nowadays, it is less common because there is a higher probability to fail. More precisely, the cardholders tend to realize the loss of the physical card and report that to their bank before the fraudster manages to undertake any illegitimate transactions with it. As soon as the stolen card is reported to the bank, the latter will lock the card so as it cannot be used anymore. It is particularly useful to notice that if the cardholder does not realize the loss of their card, a significant financial loss can occur. As mentioned in the introduction section the policies of some banks enforce cardholders to pay the cost of losses that occur due to an unreported credit card theft.

During online fraud only the details of the card are stolen and not the card itself. This is also known as virtual card theft. The details of the card can be used in places where the card need not be physically present like internet or phone purchases [6]. This type of credit transaction fraud is very dangerous and more difficult to prevent because fraudsters can hold credit card's information for a long period before they actual use it [7]. There is no way for the cardholder to

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know in advance that their credit card information is stolen. Therefore, this type of fraud may only be detected after one or more illegitimate transactions are taken place

MAIN BODY

There are various ways a fraudsters adapt in order to steal the information of credit cards. Some of those ways are briefly discussed below.

Skimming: Patidar et al. (2011) define skimming as the “process where the actual data on a card's magnetic stripe is electronically copied onto another” [9]. Fraudsters use special-purpose devices - also known as skimmers - to capture the information of credit cards that are encapsulated inside their magnetic stripes [8] [9]. They can use the stolen card information to create counterfeit physical cards in order to use them at actual shops or simply supply the card information at online shops [8]. Skimming can be committed by an unfaithful employee, who may swipe customer's card using the skimmer device, while the customer is at the point of sale. In the past, skimmer devices have also been introduced on ATM cash machines. In addition to that, micro-cameras have been used to record the PIN code of a cardholder during ATM transactions.

Site cloning: Fraudsters clone a legitimate website to deceive customers into placing an order with them. Since the fraudulent website seems identical to the legitimate one, the unsuspecting customers provide their credit card information to complete their order.

Consequently, fraudsters who obtained the customer's credit card information can commit credit transaction fraud whenever they wish to [9].

False merchant sites: According to Patidar et al. (2011) there are various websites that ask for credit card information in order to confirm customer's age [9]. These websites will never charge the credit cards directly but they may sell their information to fraudsters who will commit credit transaction fraud [9].

Credit card generators: These are automated programs which make use of banks' algorithms to generate credit card numbers [9]. Fraudsters can generate an arbitrary sequence of candidate numbers and then use other techniques – like trial and error – to figure out which numbers correspond to real credit card accounts.

Phishing: Refers to the spam emails that are sent by fraudsters in order to deceive their victims and obtain their personal information [9]. Fraudsters can impersonate a service provider or institute that victims collaborate with. In their email, fraudsters can make use of a convincing excuse to ask for victim's personal information including credit card details. The spam emails may also include links to fraudulent websites which again can deceive victims into revealing their personal information. Taking into account the enormous amount of spam emails that we receive at a daily basis, one can conclude that this type of fraud is still popular nowadays;

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although it has been out for many years.

Bankruptcy fraud occurs when consumers use their credit cards to spend more money that they can actually pay [1]. Credit cards can be seen as a way for consumers to borrow money from their banks. Normally consumers will use their credit cards to carry out daily transactions. At a regular basis – for instance once every month – the bank will send a bill to their customers in order to request a payment for their credit card transactions. Customers, who plan to commit bankruptcy fraud, will overdraw their credit card accounts and then declare themselves as being in a position of a personal bankruptcy [1]. In such a case the bank will have to pay for all the losses [1].

Xiong et al. (2013) state that bankruptcy fraud increases expeditiously and can cause serious losses to credit card issuer banks [10]. In addition, they suggest the evaluation of credit card applications in order to verify the creditworthiness of applicants [10]. Such an evaluation can usually reveal the possibility of a customer to go bankrupt in the future. Xiong et al. (2013) also state that the abovementioned evaluation is not enough because customers with initial good creditworthiness can still be proved insolvent at a later stage [10]. Therefore, even if an applicant, who satisfies the desirable levels of creditworthiness, is provided with a credit card account, the latter should keep being inspected by the bank in order to predict any possibility of future insolvency. More details about the

techniques of predicting bankruptcy fraud can be found in section 2.2.

Whittaker et al. (2005) claim that a missed payment on a credit card bill is an indication of an insolvent customer [11]. Banks should take immediate measures to reduce the potential losses in case of a customer's bankruptcy. An example of those measures could be the reduction of allowed credit card limit. Of course, banks need to be very careful when taking restricting measures against their customers. That's because there is a danger to lose customers who did not intend to commit bankruptcy fraud but for some reason, they were unable to pay their bills on time [11].

Credit bureau: A way of evaluating the creditworthiness of a credit card applicant is by considering the reports of a credit bureau. Credit bureaux are organizations which gather information about consumers from various different sources like financial institutions, banks, credit unions, courts and bankruptcy filings [1]. Banks can request a report from a credit bureau by providing the details of a credit card applicant. Delamaire et al. (2009) state that a credit report can contain "personal particulars, details of non-compliance with contractual obligations, information from public directories and additional positive information such as repayment of loans according to contract at or before maturity" [1]. Information like current home address and occupation details may also be included in the credit report [1].

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Data Mining describes the concept of data mining and the techniques which are found in the literature for detecting credit card fraud. The main reason why these techniques are reviewed is that they will form the basis of the ontology and they will be reported by the expert system as an implementation advice concerning a particular situation.

Data mining: Refers to a family of machine learning techniques capable to analyse and extract non-trivial patterns from data [15]. Data mining is also known as knowledge discovery because it can reveal previously unknown information which was hidden in the data of various databases [15]. The mined information can be proved very useful for the organizations who apply data mining. Based on the results, organizations may make important decisions which can help them survive in the competitive environment. For instance, an organization can analyse the sale records of its customers to send attractive offers on the most popular products [16].

Hormozi et al. (2004) state that "data mining enables an organization to focus on the most important information in the database, which allows managers to make more knowledge decisions by predicting future trends and behaviours" [17]. Given that databases are too large; it is very inconvenient and impractical to look manually for hidden patterns on the data [17]. Therefore, data mining can be introduced to help discover useful knowledge. Forrester

Research firm reported that 52%, of 1000 companies in total, decided to employ data mining techniques in 2001 to improve their marketing strategies; an increase of 34% comparing to 1999 [17].

Data mining can also be used to detect fraudulent credit card transactions, predict which customers are more likely to default their contractual obligations by going bankrupt as well as identify fake credit applications. Srivastava et al. (2008) state that the only way to detect credit transaction fraud is by analysing the spending behaviour of customers using data mining techniques [18]. Customers tend to follow a standard spending profile and therefore any transaction which deviates from that standard can be considered as suspicious [18]. Suspicious transactions can be examined in detailed by bank officers to determine whether they are indeed fraudulent or not.

Like most of the machine learning algorithms, data mining techniques tend to learn models from data. There are three approaches on learning the data mining models. Those are the supervised learning, the unsupervised learning and the semi-supervised learning which are described below.

Supervised learning: This is the most common learning approach where the model is trained using pre-defined class labels [3]. In the context of credit card fraud detection, the class labels may be the "legitimate" or "fraudulent" transactions. A supervisor provides a training

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data set whose transactions are classified in advanced as belonging to the "legitimate" or the "fraudulent" class. The training set can be used to build the predicting model. Any new transaction can be compared against the model to predict its class. If the new transaction follows a similar pattern to the illegitimate behaviour - as this is described by the trained model - it will be classified as a fraudulent transaction.

One limitation of supervised learning is that it requires confidentiality on the class of each training sample. If there is a fraudulent transaction X which is misclassified by the supervisor as legitimate then the constructed model will be problematic. The same happens for a legitimate transaction which is misclassified as a fraudulent [3]. Moreover, an imbalanced distribution - also known as skewed distribution - of the class labels in the training set can result in a model which does not have a very good

predictive accuracy. Skewed distribution is the situation where there are much fewer training samples of class A than class B. Maes et al. (2002) state that fraudulent transactions are usually much fewer than legitimate ones [19]. Therefore, the problem of skewed distribution exists in the area of credit card fraud detection and supervised learning is seriously affected from that. In addition, supervised learning models cannot detect new frauds [3]. This is because the behaviour of the new fraud is unknown to the trained model and therefore the latter cannot detect it. Further training is needed on the model to learn the existence of the new frauds. Finally, a substantial effort is required from experienced people - also known as supervisors - to derive the labelled training samples which will be used to construct the model [20].

Figure 1: Supervised Learning

Unsupervised learning: Unsupervised learning involves no class labels for model

construction. Bolton et al. (2002) explain that unsupervised learning techniques aim to

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discover those instances "whose behaviour is unusual" [3]. A model which represents the "baseline distribution of normal behaviour" is constructed without using class labels [3]. That model is then used to detect instances which deviate from that normal behaviour [3]. It is particularly useful to notice that unsupervised

learning techniques can detect both old and new fraud types since they are not bounded to the fraud patterns that are encapsulated in the labelled training samples like supervised learning techniques do. Instead unsupervised learning techniques aim to detect anything which does not comply with the normal behaviour.

Figure 2: Unsupervised Learning

Semi-supervised learning: Supervised learning requires all the training samples to have their class labelled. In contrast unsupervised learning needs no labelled samples at all. Semi-supervised learning lies between supervised and unsupervised learning since it involves a small number of labelled samples and a large number of unlabelled samples [20]. In the context of credit card fraud detection, semi-supervised learning techniques may involve labels for some of the legitimate transactions only. This can reduce the effort needed by supervisors to classify training data [20].

Figure 3: Semi-supervised Learning

Detection Techniques subsection provides a brief discussion on various data mining techniques which can be used to detect credit card fraud. It is particularly useful to notice that the algorithmic details of these techniques are out of the scope of this report. What is more important for this project is to understand the techniques at a higher level and extract useful characteristics which can be used to build the knowledge base. The extracted characteristics belong to the interim product which is discussed in section 3. Here there is a general discussion over the detection techniques.

Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs):An artificial neural network imitates the way that human brain works [21]. It consists of a number of nodes – which are called neurons - and edges

which interconnect those neurons [22]. Neurons are computational units which process some input information and produce some output [22]. The output of one neuron is passed as input to another. A neuron of human brain is activated if and only if the received signal is sufficiently strong [22]. Likewise, an artificial neuron receives not only some input signals but also a weight which determines whether the input signals are sufficiently strong or not. If the signals are strong enough, an activation function will start executing to produce the output [22]. Figure 4 which is taken from [22] illustrates the structure of a single artificial neuron. It shows the inputs, weights, activation function and output.

Figure 4: Artificial Neuron Structure [22]

Support Vector Machines (SVMs): Support Vector Machines is a binary classification methodology. This means that an input sample can be classified into one out of two possible classes. It is suitable for credit card fraud detection because only two classes are needed; namely the "legitimate" and "fraudulent" class. SVM tries to calculate an optimal hyperplane which will separate the samples of the two classes [23]. There are various hyperplanes which can do that job but an optimal hyperplane will also maximize the margins between the

samples of the two classes [24]. Figure 5 which is taken from [24] illustrates an example of two classes which are separated by an optimal hyperplane. Blue and black bullets correspond to the samples of the two distinct classes. Support vectors define the boundaries of each class by taking into account the sample which is closest to the hyperplane [24]. Clearly the separating hyperplane lies in the middle of support vectors by maximizing the margin between them [24]. A new sample is classified by measuring its distance from the hyperplane.

Figure 5: SVM Optimal Hyperplane [22]

According to Wu et al. (2007), SVM "has a sound theoretical foundation" which makes it a robust classification technique [25]. Nevertheless, an optimal hyperplane which separates linearly the samples of the two classes is not always possible to be found [26]. In that situation a kernel function can be used to map the non-linearly separable data into a higher dimension in which an optimal hyperplane can be found [26]. The main issue with kernel functions is that they increase the implementation complexity of SVMs.

Bayesian Belief Networks (BBNs):A

Bayesian belief network is a probabilistic classifier which is based on directed acyclic graph (DAG) [21]. The nodes of the graph represent domain variables [27]. Those are actually the attribute values that exist on the dataset [27]. Probabilistic dependencies between the nodes are represented by the edges that connect those nodes [27]. Two nodes are said to be conditionally independent if and only if there are no any edges to interconnect them [21]. BBNs make use of the conditional probability theory. In the context of credit card fraud detection, a BBN will represent the probability of a

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fraudulent transaction given that the variables of that transaction have some specific values.

According to Cheng et al. (2001) the main advantage of BBNs is that they can easily be interpreted by humans who can modify them in case they need to achieve a better predictive accuracy [27].

Decision Trees (DTS): A decision tree is a supervised learning data mining technique which repeatedly partitions the training samples into more identical groups based on a dissimilarity measure [26]. There are many different algorithms which can be used to split the training samples into branch-like groups

[28]. The resulting model has a tree-like structure consisting of a root, a number of branches, nodes and leaves. Figure 6 which is taken from [29], illustrates an example of a decision tree for playing tennis. The root is the "Outlook" node while "Humidity" and "Wind" are the subsequent nodes of the tree. The branches are "Sunny", "Overcast", "Rain", "High", "Normal", "Strong" and "Weak". The leaves which are found in the bottom of the tree are "Yes" and "No". For each leaf *L*, there is a unique path from tree's root to *L* indicating the decision rule for classifying a new sample as belonging to the class of *L* [28]. An example of a decision rule is: "IF Outlook = 'Sunny' AND Humidity = 'Normal' then class = 'Yes'".

Figure 6: An example of Decision Tree [29]

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One important advantage of decision trees over other data mining techniques is the ease of interpretability by humans. Taking into account that a decision tree can be represented either as a tree-like structure or as a set of "IF...THEN" decision rules; one can conclude that it can be easily understood in either form [26].

On the other hand, decision trees are known to be instable. According to [30], a "small fluctuations in the data sample may result in large variations in the classifications assigned to the instances" [30]. Moreover, the resulting decision tree may contain some errors or anomalies and pruning may be needed to resolve those issues [31]. Pruning is the process of removing erroneous branches, nodes or leaves. This is a tricky process because it may result in

degradation of classification performance of the tree [31].

Outlier Detection (OD): Hawkins et al. (2002) define outlier as "an observation that deviates so much from other observations as to arouse suspicion that it was generated by a different mechanism" [32]. Outlier detection refers to a family of unsupervised learning data mining techniques capable to discover rare patterns in data - also known as outliers [21]. Outliers can be detected without knowing the data set's distribution or needing any labelled training samples [33]. Figure 7 which is taken from [34], illustrates a graph which has an outlier – that is the pullet which deviates a lot from the rest of pullets.

Figure 7: An Example of an Outlier [34]

Complexity of outlier detection lies in the fact that a similarity metric needs to carefully be

chosen [2]. This will calculate the similarity between different data [2]. Different metrics

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often lead to different outcomes and therefore choosing the right metric can proved a complex task [2].

In the context of credit card fraud detection, a fraudulent transaction can be seen as an outlier which behaves differently comparing to legitimate transactions; hence it can easily be spotted.

Peer Group Analysis (PGA): Peer group analysis is an unsupervised learning technique which monitors "behaviour over time" [36]. In the context of credit card fraud detection,PGA identifies all those accounts A that used to behave similarly to a target account c at some time t_{past} in the past [2]. The accounts A are known as the "peer group" of c. The target account c is marked as suspicious if, and only if, at current time $t_{current}$ it demonstrates a different behaviour than this of its peer group A [3]. The rationale behind this approach is that a sudden change in the spending behaviour of a customer at some specific time in the year will not be marked as suspicious if a similar change occurs to its peer group at the same time [2]. The spending behaviour of most customers changes during special circumstances like Christmas and Easter periods; causing most fraud detection systems to produce false alarms [2]. PGA eliminates those false alarms by reporting only

those accounts that are indeed suspicious comparing to their peer groups.

Hidden Markov Model (HMM): Srivastava et al. (2008) defined HMM as "a double embedded stochastic process with two hierarchy level" [18]. Comparing to a conventional Markov model HMM is much more expressive and can represent more complex stochastic processes [18]. HMMs are widely used in the area of speech recognition, computer vision and pattern recognition [37]. HMMs have also been applied in the area of credit card fraud detection by Srivastava et al. (2008) [18].

Figure 8 which is taken from [38] illustrates an example of a traditional Markov model. Markov models consist of states, observations and probabilistic transitions. There are three states in figure 8; those are "Bull", "Bear" and "Even". There are also three observations; "up", "down" and "unchanged". Each state emits a specific observation; for instance, "Bull" emits "up". The transitions indicate the probability of switching between states. For example, the probability of switching to state "Bear" is 0.2 given that the current state is "Bull". If a sequence of observations like "unchanged-down-up-down" is emitted, one can easily conclude that they have been produced by states "Even-Bear-Bull-Bear" [38].

Figure 8: Traditional Markov Model Example [38]

Using ANN: Wiese et al. (2009) suggest an implementation of ANNs for detecting smart card transaction fraud [44]. Their implementation takes into account a sequence of transactions that have occurred at some time in the past, in order to determine whether a new transaction is legitimate or fraudulent [44]. They believe that "looking at individual transactions" only is misleading since it cannot face any periodical changes in spending behaviour of a customer [44]. They call their approach as "Long Short-term Memory Recurrent Neural Network (LSTM)" [44].

Guo et al. (2008) suggest a different implementation of ANNs by converting the

training samples into confidence values using a specific mathematical formula and then supply these values to train the ANN – instead of the original training samples [45]. They call their approach as "confidence-based neural network" and they claim that it can achieve promising results in detecting smart card transaction fraud [45].

Another implementation of ANNs is suggested by Patidar et al. (2011) [9]. They use the genetic algorithm - the details of which can be found in [46] - in order to derive the optimal parameters of ANN [9]. Like many other data mining techniques, ANNs make use of a number of parameters which need to be specified by

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software developers. Although the values of these parameters can seriously affect the predicting accuracy of ANN models; a standard practice for specifying these parameters has never been established [9]. The use of genetic algorithm which is suggested by Patidar et al. (2011) [9] can help in deciding these optimal parameters. They call their approach as "Genetic Algorithm Neural Network (GANN)" [9].

Using SVM: Chen et al. (2006) suggest an implementation of SVM which they call "Binary Support Vector System (BSVS)" [47]. One of the main problems of data mining techniques arises in situations where the training samples have an imbalanced distribution - also known as skewed distribution. In such a case the misclassification rate is increased whereas the predicting accuracy of the classifier is reduced. The approach of Chen et al. (2006) is insensitive to skewed distribution of training samples [47].

An innovative implementation of SVMs for detecting smart card transaction fraud is also suggested by Chen et al. (2004) [48]. They suggest the smart card issuer banks to ask their new customers to fill some questionnaires that can help them understand the spending habits of the customers [48]. This is particularly useful since there is no any prior history on the spending behaviour of new customers and therefore the detection techniques cannot spot fraudulent transactions at the initial stage [48]. Therefore, the answers to the questionnaires can be used in a similar manner to the historical

information of each customer. They call their approach as "Questionnaire-Responded Transaction Model" (QRT Model) [48].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The complete system uses three different artificial intelligence techniques. Therefore, it is important to correctly define the best parameter settings for each of the techniques and then integrate them into a complete system of the results

Autoencoder

First phase is to find architecture for an Autoencoder, which is in charge of extracting and compressing characteristics of the data which serves as the basis of the fraud detection system. Figure 24 shows the Autoencoder interface. Table 8.1 shows accuracy obtained of training phase during 100 epochs. The best configuration is 0.9 value of learning rate with 56 numbers of neurons in the hidden layer.

Mediator Network

The second step is to find the best architecture to train a mediator network with a single hidden layer. Entire dataset is used of which 80 % is given for training and 20% for testing. Figure 25 presents accuracy results of training (100 epochs) and testing phase.

Results showed that the best architecture has 25 neurons in the hidden layer, because the mean accuracy remains at 95.4%, which is the highest value in testing phase. This test shows that a simple neural network is not even capable of correctly classifying the small set of selected

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data, so it serves as a starting point to look for a more complex architecture. The interface of this

neural network can be seen in the Figure 25.

Figure 23: Interface of Autoencoder with 15 neurons in the hidden layer

Number of neurons	Learning Rate		Number of neurons	Learning Rate	
	0,5	0,9		0,5	0,9
10	98,90	99,62	37	99,07	99,93
11	98,91	99,65	38	99,07	99,93
12	98,92	99,68	39	99,08	99,93
13	98,95	99,72	40	99,09	99,93
14	98,96	99,78	41	99,10	99,93
15	98,96	99,8	42	99,10	99,93
16	98,96	99,81	43	99,11	99,93
17	98,97	99,83	44	99,11	99,93
18	98,97	99,85	45	99,12	99,93
19	98,98	99,87	46	99,12	99,94
20	98,99	99,89	47	99,13	99,94
28	99,00	99,89	48	99,13	99,94
29	99,01	99,9	49	99,14	99,94
30	99,02	99,91	50	99,15	99,95
31	99,03	99,92	51	99,16	99,95
32	99,03	99,92	52	99,18	99,95
33	99,03	99,93	53	99,18	99,95
34	99,04	99,93	54	99,18	99,96
35	99,04	99,93	55	99,19	99,96
36	99,04	99,93	56	99,20	99,99

Table: Accuracy Obtained Training Autoencoder

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Figure 24: Interface of Mediator with 11 neurons in the hidden layer

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Number of neurons	Training		Testing	
	Learning Rate 0,5	Learning Rate 0,9	Learning Rate 0,5	Learning Rate 0,9
7	93,1	95,6	91,1	92,8
8	93,2	96	91,3	93,4
9	93,2	96,6	91,2	95,2
10	93,3	96,1	91,5	94,9
11	93,4	97,7	91,5	94
12	93,5	96,1	91,7	93,4
13	93,6	96,4	91,8	92,6
14	93,8	96,1	91,9	95
15	94,1	96,7	92	93,4
16	94,2	96,4	92,2	93,2
17	94,2	96	92,3	93,3
18	94,4	96,2	92,4	94
19	94,6	96,3	92,5	94,2
20	94,7	96,3	92,5	94,5
21	94,9	96,4	92,8	94,6
22	95,2	96,5	93	94,8
23	95,3	96,5	93,2	95
24	95,5	96,5	93,5	95,2
25	95,6	98.2	93,8	96,7
26	95,9	96,6	94	95,3

Table: Accuracy obtained training and Testing Mediator Network

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Figure 25: Interface of Agent with 15 neurons in the hidden layer

Agent

The final step is to find the best architecture to train an agent using reinforcement learning. Entire dataset is used of which 80% is given for training and 20% for testing. Table 24 presents accuracy results of training (1000 episodes) and testing phase.

Results showed that the best architecture has 15 neurons in the hidden layer, because the mean accuracy remains at 98.1% – 98.9% using lambda value equal to 0.1 and discount factor equal to 0.9. Another important value is size replay memory (M) which is set equal to 200000. Learning rate equal to 0.9 is used because this value shows better performance in this type of networks.

Test shows that an agent needs preprocessed data which allows a better extraction of features

and therefore better performance. The interface of this agent can be seen in the Figure 24.

Final Results

The proposed **Smart Card Fraud Detector** uses three components: Autoencoder, Mediator Network and Agent. The purpose of the system is to improve the performance of each of the components, especially the agent, since it shows that it needs to improve its accuracy and this is possible with a prior data processing. This preprocessing is achieved using the characteristics extracted by an Autoencoder and the first classification made by the mediator network which serves to reduce and adjust the weights coming from the autoencoder. Finally the agent makes the final classification.

After many tests to determine parameter setting, table 26 shows a general summary, which defines

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the best parameter settings for the system and also shows the best result, which is given by the *accuracy* of the system.

Number of neurons	Training		Testing		Training		Testing	
	lambda (λ)				Discount factor (γ)			
	0,1	0,9	0,1	0,9	0,1	0,9	0,1	0,9
7	98	96,5	95,8	94,5	97,8	98	96,8	97
8	98,2	96,8	96,1	94,6	97,9	98	96,9	97,2
9	98,2	96,8	96,4	94,8	98	98,1	97	97,3
10	98,3	96,9	96,5	94,8	98,1	98,2	97,1	97,5
11	98,4	97	97	94,9	98,2	98,3	97,1	97,5
12	98,5	97,2	97,2	95	98,4	98,4	97,2	97,6
13	98,6	97,3	97,5	95,1	98,5	98,5	97,4	97,6
14	98,7	97,4	97,6	95,2	98,5	98,6	97,5	97,7
15	98,9	97,5	98,1	95,2	98,5	98,9	97,6	98.1
16	98,9	97,6	97,6	95,3	98,5	98,8	97,5	97
17	98,8	97,8	97,6	95,4	98,6	98,6	97,6	97,7
18	98,7	97,8	97,5	95,5	98,5	98,6	97,6	97,6
19	98,6	98	97,5	95,6	98,6	98,6	97,5	97,6

Table 26: Accuracy Obtained by training and testing Agents

	Autoencoder	Mediator Network	Agent
Input Layer	28	56	25
Hidden Layer	56	25	15
Output Layer	28	2	2
Learning Algorithm	Backpropagation	Backpropagation	Deep Q-learning
Transfer Function	Sigmoid	Sigmoid	Sigmoid
Loss Function	MSE	MSE	$(y_j - Q(s_j, a_j; \theta))^2$
Learning Rate	0.9	0.9	0.9
Discount factor (γ)	N/A	N/A	0.9
Lambda value (λ)	N/A	N/A	0.1
Size replay memory (M)	N/A	N/A	200000

Table 27: General Specifications of Smart card fraud detector

Values were measured in training and testing phase using whole imbalanced database. Figure 25 shows how the error of each component: AE, MN and Agent begins to decrease while increasing the number of epochs. Figure 25 shows how the accuracy value of each component grows until it reaches values that validate that the system is fully functional and reliable.

Comparison with Other Algorithms

There are other algorithms that use the same

dataset to detect fraud. The difference with Smart Card Fraud Detector is that they use methods to balance the database: hybrid sampling and random sampling [19]. Smart Card Fraud Detector when using the imbalanced dataset is more adaptable to the real problems that arise in bank transactions. Table below shows a comparison of the accuracy values obtained between these algorithms.

Figure 26: Error of three main components

	Accuracy	
	Training	Testing
Auto-encoder	99.9	96.4
Mediator Network	98.2	96.7
Agent	98.9	98.1

Table: Results of Smart Card Fraud Detector

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Figure 27: Accuracy of three Main components

Classifiers	Accuracy
Logistic Regression	96.2*
Naive Bayes	96.9*
Decision Tree	96.4*
K-Nearest Neighbour	99.1*
Q-Credit Card Fraud Detector	98.1

Table: Comparison with other existing algorithms

Balanced dataset

Finally, the Figure 28 shows the proposed system interface, friendly and simple software that allows

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the user to have an easy interaction.

Figure 28: Interface of Smart Card Fraud Detector

CONCLUSION

Nowadays the use of credit cards increases uncontrollably, being one of the most popular online and regular purchase payment methods. Because of this, credit card fraud also begins to grow. Every day a large number of transactions occur which are sources of a great deal of information which, together with analysis techniques and human resources, can be used to concentrate attention on investigating suspicious behaviour.

Credit card fraud is a problem that requires a lot of research interest because it causes a big loss of money for users and banks. Fraud detection is a particularly challenging and complex task because fraudsters also innovate in their fraud

techniques to generate more innovative systems that help stop them. For this reason it is necessary to find methods to guarantee the security of cardholders when they use their credit cards to make purchases or electronic payments.

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